

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF RHEOLOGICAL PARAMETERS IN CHRONIC HEART FAILURE PATIENTS: A REVIEW ARTICLE

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ABSTRACT

Heart failure is a complex clinical syndrome that leads to reduced cardiac contractility or filling capacity of the heart. About 64 million people worldwide suffer from heart failure. The prevalence of heart failure varies with age. In developed countries, the incidence of age-related heart failure is declining due to better management of cardiovascular diseases, but morbidity and prognosis still appear to be undesirable. It is very important to identification of the etiological factors in the process of effective management and treatment. In this abstract, we have analyzed the expected changes in rheological parameters, specifically in phenotypes and functional classes, as predictors of the severity of the disease in patients with chronic heart failure.

Keywords: Heart failure, Erythrocyte aggregability, Hemorheology.

INTRODUCTION

In terms of prevalence, diseases of the cardiovascular system (CVDs) are in the first place in the world. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 17.9 million people die from this cause every year [1]. Heart failure appears to be one of the significant pathologies of cardiac function. This pathological condition can be caused by damage to the myocardium, pericardium, endocardium, valvular apparatus, and the great vessels of the heart [2]. Heart failure has been a subject of ongoing interest for the medical community since it was singled out as an emerging new epidemic in 1997 [3]. The prevalence of heart failure is increasing over time [4]. The mortality rate due to heart failure ranges from 25% to 75% per year [5]. The development of the disease to some extent depends on age, genetic, social, and subclinical factors. Symptoms of heart failure are mainly associated with a wide range of left ventricular function impairment, which can vary from its normal size, volume, and preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF) to dilated ventricles with increased volumes and low ejection fraction (low EF) [6]. A cohort study combining the Framingham Heart Study (FHS) and the Cardiovascular Health Study (CHS) showed a 67% mortality rate within 5 years after diagnosis [7].

The overall prognosis of a mild – moderate reduced ejection fraction is better than that of an impaired one [8]. The most common causes of heart failure are ischemic heart disease and myocardial infarction, arterial hypertension, and valvular pathologies; other causes include familial cardiopathies and congenital and genetic heart diseases, myocarditis, autoimmune and rheumatoid causes, chemotherapy, other cardiotoxic drugs, infiltrative heart diseases, endocrine or metabolic abnormalities [9-11].

The prognosis of patients with heart failure is not optimistic if the underlying pathology is not corrected;

Half of such patients die within 4 years, and 50% of the patients with severe heart failure die within 1 year [12]; The functional class of heart failure is characterized by a tendency to worsen. Symptoms of the disease undergo negative changes despite therapeutical options and left ventricular function. Rarely do not clinical symptoms correspond to the grade of heart muscle dysfunction. However, their persistence under the background of therapy indicates an unfavorable prognosis [13]; In the given study, we aimed to identify expected changes in hemorheological properties according to heart failure phenotypes and functional classes to determine the possible role of hemorheological parameters in the detection of heart failure at an early stage to treat it efficiently.

Heart failure is a progressive pathology. It is a huge and growing problem in the world. Diagnosis of heart failure is based on history and physical examination; Heart failure is defined by the European Association of Cardiology as follows: a combination of clinical symptoms at rest or during exercise, which is caused by the systolic or diastolic dysfunction of the heart which is objectively confirmed by imaging studies [14];

Heart failure is not a disease but a syndrome – a combination of signs and symptoms – caused by the failure of the heart to pump blood to support the circulatory system at rest or during activity, which is caused by the systolic or diastolic dysfunction of the heart muscle, and which is objectively confirmed by imaging studies [14]; The simplest terminology used to describe the severity of heart failure is the New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional classification [15].

It should be noted that the classification depends only on the symptoms. According to pathophysiological mechanisms, heart failure is caused by myocardial systolic or diastolic dysfunction, or both [16]; From the

etiological point of view, left ventricular failure, isolated right ventricular failure, and biventricular heart failure are distinguished [17];

Traditionally, separate phenotypes of heart failure have been distinguished based on the values of the left ventricular ejection fraction [18]; three groups of phenotypes are distinguished: Group I - patients with heart failure with severely reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF), where the fraction is less than 40% ($LVEF \leq 40\%$), Group II - patients with mildly reduced ejection fraction (HFmrEF), in this group the value of the fraction is 41%-49% and Group III - patients with preserved ejection fraction (HFpEF), where the value is equal/higher than 50% ($LVEF \geq 50\%$), but the patients have clinical symptoms and signs of heart failure, confirmed structural and/or functional impairment of the heart and/or elevated blood natriuretic peptide levels (NPs) [19].

To diagnose the disease, special attention is paid to the presence of typical cardiac symptoms, such as difficulty breathing, orthopnea, paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea, reduced tolerance to physical exertion, fatigue, weakness, and prolonged recovery time after exercise; less typical, but still noteworthy: nocturnal cough, dry wheezing, bloating, loss of the appetite, distraction (especially in the elderly), depression, palpitations, dizziness, syncope, bendopnea [20]; Specific signs of heart failure include increased pressure in the jugular vein, wet wheezing sound in the lungs, and peripheral edema; also, hepatojugular reflux, gallop rhythm, laterally displaced apical impulse. It is important to determine the etiological factors of the disease. In patients with a probable diagnosis of heart failure, necessary investigations include:

1) Electrocardiography (a normal ECG makes the diagnosis less probable).

2) Assessment of natriuretic peptides (NPs) in plasma is recommended to confirm the diagnosis at the initial stage; A high concentration of natriuretic peptides suggests the presence of the disease. Elevated level of B-type natriuretic peptide (BNP) is associated with reduced left ventricular ejection fraction, hypertrophy, elevated filling pressure, and myocardial ischemia [21];

3) Basic screening tests such as serum urea and electrolyte, creatinine, complete blood count (CBC), urinalysis, glycosylated hemoglobin, lipid spectrum, liver, and thyroid function tests are recommended in all patients with suspected heart failure, and also chest radiography is routinely performed [14];

4) Transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) is the main method of cardiac investigation to reveal the structural and functional features of the heart. During the investigation, chamber sizes and volumes, left ventricular eccentric or concentric hypertrophy, areas of regional asynergy, global left ventricular systolic function, right ventricular function, pulmonary hypertension, valvular apparatus, left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, and its markers are evaluated, e.g., increased filling pressure [22].

Left ventricular dysfunction is caused by myocardial damage or stress and is mostly a progressive process. The geometry and structure of the chamber is

changed. A ventricular dilatation and/or ventricular hypertrophy occurs and a spherical cavity is developed [23]; Several hemodynamic changes occur during heart failure that develops in the setting of atrial fibrillation; intracardiac pressure increases and cardiac output is unequal, both during physical exertion and at rest [24,25].

In these patients, the properties of blood flow change, which is reflected in changes in hemorheological parameters [26]. Patients with reduced left ventricular ejection fraction and systolic and diastolic dysfunction are especially noteworthy; in this group of patients, several hemorheological characteristics, such as blood flow, erythrocyte aggregability, and deformability, plasma viscosity, and consequently, their role in the process of the disease progression, are insufficiently studied.

It should be noted that blood flow is nothing but a specific disposition of erythrocytes in plasma and their movement through blood vessels; Any changes in the structural characteristics of blood flow lead to increased flow resistance [27]. These changes are as follows: an increase in erythrocyte aggregation, a decrease in their deformability, and an increase in local hematocrit level and plasma viscosity.

The blood supply of any tissue of the body depends on the ability of the blood to flow, that is, on its rheological properties. It is the rheological parameters that determine the adequacy of microcirculation [28]. To evaluate hemorheological characteristics, namely erythrocyte aggregation, in this case, we use the Index of Erythrocyte Aggregability (IEA). The method "Georgian technique" was created as a result of the work of Georgian scientists and is recognized worldwide as direct, quantitative, and accurate [29].

The erythrocyte deformability index (IED) [30] is determined by the membrane filtration method. Plasma viscosity (PV) is measured at 37°C in a capillary viscometer. The movement of the plasma in the capillary is induced by the force of gravity. As a result of the identification of those parameters, it becomes possible to evaluate the microcirculation of capillaries [28]. The microcirculatory bed is a complex organized system. In this system, a network of blood flow and distribution (arterioles and pre-capillary sphincters), a metabolic network (capillaries), a depot (postcapillary blood vessels and venules), and a drainage network (lymphatic capillaries and pre-capillaries) are distinguished; Pathology of the microcirculatory bed involves vascular, intravascular and extravascular changes [31];

Capillary hydrostatic pressure does not always correspond to systemic blood pressure and may change during pathological conditions regardless of changes in blood pressure levels [30]; During pathological conditions, the leading role is assigned to the difficulty of blood backflow, which is carried out by contractile force or mechanical pressure from postcapillary blood vessels - venules and veins. An important role in maintaining tissue perfusion in the microcirculatory system is played by the rheological properties of blood flow [32,33].

Blood flow is determined by: 1) the propulsive force of the heart 2) the strength and consistency of heart contraction 3) the functional state of blood vessels

4) the properties of the blood itself [34]; The rheological properties of blood have an equal influence on both systemic (central) hemodynamics and microhemocirculation. For the normal functioning of organs and tissues, it is necessary to ensure optimal perfusion, which cannot be achieved without the normal interaction of hemorheological and hemodynamic factors [35]. Today, it has been established that erythrocyte aggregation and the global contractile function of the cardiac muscle are inversely proportional [36].

The given study is valid during conditions diagnosed with atrial fibrillation. Rheological parameters are insufficiently investigated in patients with ischemic and other types of heart failure; The hemorheological condition is not considered during the initial diagnosis of the disease nor during performing preventive measures, and certainly not as a target of treatment. However, there are a number of scientific works that show that the violation of hemorheological characteristics is a risk factor for the development of many cardiovascular pathologies, such as hypovolemia after bleeding, cardiogenic shock, arterial hypertension, chronic ischemic heart disease [37,38]. Against this background, it is of particular interest to determine the rheological parameters concerning the course of chronic heart failure, which will allow us to manage the identified changes as well as possible.

In this abstract, we have tried to explain that it is important to evaluate the hemorheological properties of blood in patients with heart failure in order to determine their role in the detection of the disease at an early stage. There is a high possibility that the changes in rheological parameters facilitate the progression of the disease and exacerbate the disease leading to a complication, i.e. to a higher functional class of heart failure. It is important to pay attention to take into account hemorheological parameters as a treatment objective during treatment planning. Early detection of rheological changes will slow down and may even prevent severe complications of the disease.

CONCLUSIONS: In this article, we have tried to explain that it is important to evaluate the hemorheological properties of blood in patients with heart failure to determine their role in the detection of the disease at an early stage. There is a high possibility that the changes in rheological parameters facilitate the progression of the disease and exacerbate the disease, leading to a complication, i.e., a higher functional class of heart failure. It is important to evaluate the hemorheological parameters during treatment planning as a target. Early detection of rheological changes will slow down and may even prevent severe complications of the disease.

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